

High pressure and dielectric properties of the spin- $1/2$ compounds

Ba₂CuTeO₆

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Ba₂CuTeO₆ compound exhibits two phases, one is prepared at ambient pressure and other can only be synthesized under high-pressure. Sample prepared at 900°C under 6 GPa pressure crystallizes in a perovskite type structure (Fig. 1). Whereas samples prepared at ambient pressure crystallizes in triclinic structure (Fig. 1) and also show structural transition T_S around 285 K. In triclinic two-leg spin ladders are formed by the tellurium-bridged Cu²⁺($S = 1/2$) ions. With decreasing temperature, $\chi(T)$ curve displays a broad maximum at 75 K with the subsequent drop and then a small kink at $T_N = 15$ K. In addition, the real part dielectric constant $\varepsilon'(T)$ exhibit a frequency independent peak near the structural transition temperature T_S (Fig. 2). Since the dielectric properties are very sensitive to the local electric field distribution of the samples, studies of the temperature and frequency dependent dielectric behavior can provide us a better understanding about the magnetic/structural transition of this compound.

Fig. 1 X-ray diffraction of Ba₂CuTeO₆ compounds.

Fig. 2 Real permittivity vs temperature.

Keywords: Perovskite, High pressure, real permittivity, spin ladders.